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Factors Affect on Applying Environmental Auditing Intention in Vietnamese Enterprises

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Abstract

The main objective of the article is to analyze the impact of factors affecting the intention of applying environmental auditing in Vietnamese enterprises using the Theory of Planning Behavior (TPB). From the theoretical basis and the legal basis which are synthesized, combined with the experimental results, the author proposes recommendations for businesses as well as agencies to improve the attitude and ability of Vietnamese enterprises in applying environmental audit.

Keywords: Environmental auditing, Vietnam

1. Introduction

The economic, political and social development in recent years has been enormous, however, it has not been paralleled with the preservation of the environment. There have been many cases of violations caused by the activities of businesses, causing heavy impacts on the environment. Faced with this situation, it is urgent to have a solution to raise awareness of businesses. Environmental auditing (EA) can be the solution in this case since it helps to minimize the negative impacts that businesses cause on the environment, as the results of previous studies have shown. However, EA is only applied voluntarily and there are no laws requiring them to be mandatory.

The factors affecting the voluntary application of environmental auditing come from many aspects, but in this article, the author uses the model "Theory of Planned Behavior" and concludes that the following three factors have an influence on the enterprises' intention to apply EA, that is: attitude towards the behavior, subjective norm and perceived behavioral control.

2. Literature review

During this research, the author raised the following questions: What is environmental audit? What factors affect the intention of enterprises to apply EA? Is the intention to adopt EA different among business groups? What difficulties are businesses facing when applying EA in Vietnam? What is the solution to those problems? Through the study of the overview and the current situation, the theoretical basis of environmental auditing as well as the analysis used in the article, the above questions are successively answered. In addition, the author also gives practical recommendations to solve the difficulties that businesses are facing as well as contributions to improve the application of EA in Vietnam today.

Research overview: Gray et al. conducted a study to explain the environmental problems of companies (Gray, et al., 2001). Through research papers and collected analysis results, the authors find that

multinational companies and companies operating in the field of raw materials often take advantage of voluntary disclosure. They concluded that: Disclosure of information on the environment is an effective tool for businesses to use simultaneously for many different purposes, namely avoiding costs incurred during operation. The second factor that strongly influences the intention of enterprises to apply EA is institutional responsibility and sanctions if they violate. Mishra and others organized an investigation into the penalized companies face if they violate environmental regulations (Mishra, et al., 1997). To prove this point, previous studies have focused on assessing the compliance level of companies. Regarding the conditional penalty structure, efforts to avoid environmental damage and voluntarily disclose such damage have reduced fines. On the contrary, being found in violation, accused and found guilty will sometimes adversely affect the reputation of the company. Therefore, conditional penalties often have a positive effect on an enterprise's willingness to perform environmental audit because of its beneficial nature. It is not only legal and policy factors that affect companies' intention to apply environmental auditing. In their study, Gabel and Sinclair-Desgagné showed that compensation pressure, penalty pressure or payment pressure in general greatly influence the intention to adopt EA (Gabel & Sinclair-Desgagné, 1994). In addition to the above factors, factors in terms of geography and size also affect the intention to apply environmental auditing of the company, but the influence is not too significant.

In the 70s and 80s of the 20th century, many countries face with the problem of environmental pollution and environmental protection. The US is the first to adopt EA as an environmental management tool. The design of numerous EA laws have paved the way for the development of EA throughout the US market. Many environmental managers of companies have developed and used internal environmental audits as a tool to reduce costs and legal liability for non-compliance with environmental protection regulations. Faced with the need for a common and unified environmental management system for countries around the world, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) has developed and published a set of ISO 14000 standards on environmental management systems in 1996. The primary purpose of it is to assist organizations in preventing the environmental impacts arising from the production, distribution and consumption of their products or services.

While plenty of previous researches have paid their attention to EA in more developed countries, little is studied about EA application and the factors affecting the action in developing countries, specifically in Vietnam. Small developing countries (SDCs) suffer far more severe consequences than developed countries. They face financial difficulties which can be a "stepping stone" for them in managing environment-related issues and above all, voluntarily undertake and have the capacity to carry out environmental audit procedures. In Vietnam, the voluntary implementation of EA and disclosure of environmental information is still very limited. Many serious cases are handled transiently and temporarily; there are no official written instructions or regulations of the State on handling instructions or handling environmental auditing; a national environmental data bank has not yet been established to serve as a basis for comparison and recommendations of auditors.

Theoretical background: Environmental auditing is still a new concept. The main objective of EA is to examine and evaluate the compliance level of companies, organizations and individuals related to environmental protection and management activities. There are two common ways to classify environmental auditing, which are EA based on the audit subject and EA based on the audit object. Currently, environmental audit in Vietnam mainly stops at the audit of industrial waste and has not approached other audit objectives that have been performed in the world such as the audit of the environmental management system.

In terms of legal and regulations, there is no specific Vietnamese law for EA. This audit is only mentioned in other laws and sub-laws. However, the significance of EA has been strongly emphasized by the State Audit of Vietnam. In addition, the ISO 14000 standard is also an effective tool in assessing the environmental activities of enterprises. The ISO 14000 system of environmental management systems has been applied by more and more production and business establishments. In the provisions of this ISO set,

participating companies and factories are required to conduct internal environmental audits for their entire environmental management system. This is an opportunity for environmental auditing to develop in our country in the coming time. With the support of international standard ISO 14000, regulations on environmental management systems, including regulations on environmental audit, along with the participation of universities and researchers, it is promised that in the near future, EA will become an effective and popular environmental management tool in our country.

Research methods: In this article, the author applies sampling and quantitative research methods. The research model was built by the author, based on the original model built by Ajzen and his coworkers on Theory of Planned Behavior. In the model, there are three independent variables, which are attitude towards the behavior (AT), subjective norm (SN) and perceived behavioral control (PBC), which affect one dependent variable, namely behavioral intention (BI). Besides, there are four types of enterprises that have influence on the intention of companies. The model is presented by the author as follows:

Source: Authors

From the intrinsic relationship between the factors in the proposed model, the study builds the following **hypotheses:**

H1: Attitude towards behavior has a positive influence on the intention to apply environmental audit, that is, the more positive the attitude will promote the intention to apply and vice versa.

H2: Subjective norms refer to the influences and factors that can affect the intention of the business. Subjective norm was found to have a direct positive influence on the firm's intention to apply environmental **audit.**

H3: Perceived behavioral control is defined as an individual's/business's confidence in the ability to perform behaviors. Perceived behavioral control has a positive effect on the intention to apply environmental audit of enterprises.

Descriptive statistics: In an online survey sent to businesses in the North of Vietnam, from April to May 2022, 193 votes were collected. The author selected 150 valid and most informative votes for analysis.

Statistical results show that small and medium-sized companies with the number of years of operation from 5 to 10 years, operating in the manufacturing sector (fields related to materials) tend to apply EA the most.

Quantitative research: After preliminary testing the scale by Cronbach's Alpha coefficient, the author concluded the reliability of 19/20 scale and continued to run Exploratory factor analysis (EFA). The results for 15 indicators of the three independent variables and four indicators of the dependent variable are qualified with the Eigenvalues of all factors meeting the requirements. The author also obtained the adjusted R-squared coefficient equal 0.63, which means that the built-in multiple linear regression model is suitable for the data set of 63.0%. In other words, 63.0% of Intention can be explained by the impact of 3 factors: AT, SN and PBC. The author obtained the regression equation with normalized beta:

$$BI = 0.304 AT + 0.455 SN + 0.344 PBC$$

Regression analysis results show that, all three factors attitude towards the behavior ($\beta_1 = 0,304$), subjective norm ($\beta_2 = 0,455$) and perceived behavioral control ($\beta_3 = 0,344$) have a positive influence on intention to apply EA; it can be seen that, the subjective norm factor has the most impact and the attitude factor has the least impact. The author evaluates the causes of this result and concludes as follows: External factors and objects that have a strong impact on enterprises, such as customer evaluation, institutional pressure, key pressure government, etc., have a great influence on the intention to apply EA of enterprises. Enterprises tend to consider pressures coming from external objects, which are the main objects affecting their business results as well as their operations. Therefore, the subjective norm factor is the most influential factor. On the contrary, this action may not come from the enterprise's own awareness of environmental protection, so the attitude towards the intention to apply EA of the enterprise is not the strongest influencing factor.

Also, Authors test the hypotheses proposed above. The reliability level of all three hypotheses is 95%, which is accepted.

3. Conclusion

According to the results, the intention to apply EA does not come from enterprises' attitude but the pressure from external factors. Therefore, attitude must be the first priority to be raised, followed by subjective norm and perceived behavioral control. The recommendations are given for three factors as follows:

In terms of attitude, it is necessary to make the administrators feel that the application of EA is very useful and practical. There are many ways to influence attitudes, such as propaganda through media programs, raising knowledge and awareness through books, courses, etc. Environmental auditing results will contribute to raising awareness and increasing people's attention to macro issues such as factors affecting the common living environment. The disclosure of auditing information will help businesses and organizations improve the quality of products and services, towards sustainable development.

In terms of subjective norm, it is necessary to show them the "double benefit" that can be gained from applying EA. The best way is to build a "Forum on Environmental Auditing" on a reputable website, shared by scientists, especially successful entrepreneurs, good CEOs and must be supported by the media and promoted to many administrators or lecturers, students and trainees.

In terms of perceived behavioral control, it needs to be affected by external factors to be effective and influential. Awareness of improving application capacity through scientific measures, including the application of EA, needs to be actively promoted by the media and spread messages that promote businesses to innovate, change thinking, scientific management, not based on feelings, so that they have the motivation to change, try to build and invest appropriate resources for the application of EA.

In Vietnam, the voluntary application of EA and disclosure of environmental information by enterprises is still very limited. Vietnam also does not have a specific legal document stipulating that the State Audit has the function of environmental auditing; awareness and public opinion about the field of EA is still limited, especially among the subjects of state management agencies in charge of the environment. In order to

overcome the limitations and continue to implement well the application of EA in the coming time, it is necessary to note the following key solutions: Firstly, increase the awareness of agencies, units and society about EA; promote propaganda to raise awareness of state management agencies and the public. Secondly, propose and develop legal documents specifying the environmental audit function of the State Audit; formulate and develop environmental auditing guidelines and methods in the direction of compliance with the system of international auditing standards. Thirdly, focus on building and strengthening environmental auditing capacity; develop contingency of staff of environmental auditors to ensure sufficient quantity, professional structure and reasonable industry structure.

Conclusion: Applying environmental auditing not only helps businesses comply with regulations, but also helps businesses better implement regulations on environmental protection. The implementation of environmental audit helps organizations, production facilities, business services accurately identify the shortcomings and risks related to environmental management at all stages of production and business. The application of environmental auditing as soon as possible will help businesses go further in the era of globalization, when sustainable values are upheld. Businesses taking advantage of environmental auditing will strongly benefit ahead and reinforce their positions in such a chaotic market.

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